

Report on Methodological Framework Workshop

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D5.1 Overview

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Abbreviations and acronyms

TERM	DEFINITION	TERM	DEFINITION
CA	Consortium Agreement	MFW	Methodological Framework Workshop
clCH	culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage	PC	Project Coordinator
D[No.]	Deliverable [No.]	T[No.]	Task [No.]
EC	European Commission	WP[No.]	Work Package [No.]
GA	Grant Agreement		

Consortium

ROLE	NAME	SHORT NAME	COUNTRY
Coordinator	University of Durham	UDUR	UK
Partner	Atlantic Technological University	ATU	Ireland
Partner	Barcelona Supercomputing Center	BSC	Spain
Partner	City, University of London	CITY	UK
Partner	Fundació Alícia	FA	Spain
Partner	Institut LYFE	LYFE	France
Partner	Instituto Superior Técnico	IST	Portugal
Partner	Roskilde University	RUC	Denmark
Partner	University College Cork	UCC	Ireland
Partner	University of Alicante	UA	Spain
Partner	University of Gastronomic Sciences of Pollenzo	UNISG	Italy
Partner	University of Milan	UMIL	Italy
Partner	University of Toronto	UoT	Canada

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Executive Summary

Deliverable 5.1 (D5.1) documents the conception, structure, implementation, and outcomes of the **Methodological Framework Workshop (MFW)** held at the University of Gastronomic Sciences (UNISG), Pollenzo, from 22–25 October 2025.

The workshop was organised within Work Package 5 (WP5 – Cooking: Recipes and Applications) and fulfils Task 5.1 (T5.1), which required the development of a flexible and adaptable methodological and analytical framework for the study of recipes as cultural heritage through the interconnected concepts of mobility, agency, and interdisciplinarity.

1 Introduction

RELISH (Reframing European gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage) is a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project that offers a pathway to put into practice culinary recipes and food culture as cultural and digital tools to strengthen a crucial aspect of EU's common cultural heritage. Through an innovative and systematic approach to the understanding and use of traditional EU recipes via digital and AI-powered technology, it embarks on the production of a visual and verbal food storytelling web platform that aims to mediate social cohesion, reinforce EU cultural heritage transmission both at home and abroad through education and public engagement, while addressing sustainable practices in the home kitchen and the EU hospitality sector.

Work Package 5 (WP5) – COOKING: Recipes and Applications is led by UNISG and focuses on positioning recipes as:

- Sites of learning
- Cultural mediators
- Tools for understanding European identity formation
- Instruments for sustainability and mobility analysis

The **Methodological Framework Workshop (MFW)** constitutes the foundational step of WP5 and directly fulfils the objectives of Task 5.1 (T5.1):

- Develop a methodological and analytical framework for recipe analysis
- Conceptualise recipes through mobility, agency, and interdisciplinarity
- Prepare groundwork for the recipe visualisation prototype
- Generate pedagogical materials and dissemination outputs

1.1 Description of the document

Deliverable 5.1 (D5.1) presents the conceptual foundations, structure, proceedings, and outcomes of the MFW organised by UNISG within WP5 of the RELISH project. It fulfils T5.1, which requires the development of a flexible and adaptable methodological and analytical framework for the analysis of recipes as cultural heritage through the interconnected concepts of mobility, interdisciplinarity, and agency.

Beyond event documentation, the report formalises the methodological approach of WP5. It shows how the workshop functioned as a deliberate epistemological intervention, consolidating a shared analytical vocabulary across disciplines and aligning conceptual reflection with the practical requirements of later WP5 outputs. In particular, the framework provides a basis for work under T5.2, including recipe data structures, metadata categories, and visualisation possibilities developed in dialogue with RELISH technical partners such as BSC and IST. It also supports the “Teaching with Recipes” educational materials and the forthcoming edited volume by translating workshop discussions into concrete scholarly, pedagogical, and digital outputs.

1.2 WPs and tasks related to the deliverable

- WP5 T5.1 Core task - Methodological framework development
- WP5 T5.2 - Framework informs recipe dataset and visualisation prototype
- WP5 T5.4 - Workshop materials adapted into “Teaching with Recipes” videos (educational materials)
- WP5 T5.5 - Framework forms theoretical basis for edited volume (scientific dissemination)
- WP10/11 - Dissemination Workshop served as visibility and communication milestone

As WP5 Lead, UNISG coordinated the workshop in collaboration with consortium partners.

1.3 Rationale

The MFW addressed an original and timely research need within food studies, culinary heritage, and digital humanities: to make explicit the key methodological questions that historical recipes raise across different periods, regions, media, and disciplinary traditions.

The strong response to the Call for Papers, sustained audience engagement, and rapid development of the workshop proceedings into the forthcoming volume *Recipes as Cultural Heritage* demonstrate the relevance of this topic and the demand for more concerted collaboration among research teams working on different histories of recipe production, circulation, preservation, and use.

The report also foregrounds one of the workshop's guiding methodological questions: How to distinguish between the recipe, the dish, the cookbook, the culinary practice, and the heritage object, and why these distinctions matter for historical interpretation, digital representation, and public dissemination?

By articulating how recipes are understood within RELISH as dynamic, mobile, and agentive cultural artefacts shaped by social, material, environmental, technological, and political forces, D5.1 establishes WP5's methodological framework and contributes to the broader objectives of RELISH.

Figure 1: Workshop participants listening to presentations in Aula Magna (UNISG). October 2025. Pollenzo, Italy.

1.4 Workshop Overview

The MFW event brought together 21 selected presenters (chosen from over 60 submissions) and a broader audience of between 150 participants across sessions. Structured across 8 thematic sessions, the workshop advanced a central proposition, succinctly summarised by WP5 member Daniel Newman:

“Recipes offer a uniquely productive lens through which to study cultural heritage, knowledge transmission, and everyday forms of power... Recipes are not neutral or merely functional texts, but dense cultural artefacts that mediate between material practice and symbolic meaning.”

Not only do recipes mediate between the material and the symbolic, they also mediate between individual agency and institutional power, between public and private life, and between analogue and digital forms of transmission.

The workshop consolidated a shared analytical framework for WP5, informed the conceptual foundations of the recipe visualisation prototype, and laid the groundwork for forthcoming pedagogical and dissemination outputs, including the “Teaching with Recipes” educational materials and the edited volume derived from the workshop proceedings. By refining the analytical categories that will underpin dataset construction, visualisation design, and dissemination, the workshop contributes directly to RELISH’s broader goal of developing innovative approaches to European gastronomic heritage that connect historical research, digital methodologies, sustainability, and public engagement.

Thus, the event brought together consortium partners and external scholars, supported by public figures, to refine a shared analytical vocabulary and methodological protocol that will support:

- The development of the recipe visualisation prototype (T5.2)
- “Teaching with Recipes” educational materials (T5.4)
- The edited volume and scientific dissemination outputs (T5.5)

The document was prepared by UNISG (WP5 Lead) with contributions from consortium partners, particularly the UDUR, UCC, and UoT.

In summary, this deliverable documents:

- The conceptual framework developed during the Methodological Workshop
- The design and structure of the workshop
- The methodological debates and working sessions
- The implications for subsequent WP5 tasks
- The integration of workshop outcomes into digital, pedagogical, and dissemination outputs

Figure 2: The late Carlo Petrini, founder of the Slow Food Movement and President of UNISG, addresses the Methodological Workshop audience. October 2025. Pollenzo.

2 Approach

The MFW was designed as a scholarly and structured methodological intervention. It built directly upon the critical framework developed in WP4, which identifies culinary heritage as a dynamic and evolving field characterised by tensions between documentation and practice, representation and embodiment, preservation and transformation.

Rather than treating recipes as fixed textual objects, the workshop adopted WP4's emphasis on culinary heritage as a form of cultural knowledge that is performative, relational, and situated within broader social, material, and technological contexts. The event therefore provided an opportunity to test and refine the conceptual foundations established in D4.1 by bringing together scholars from multiple disciplines to examine how recipes are conceptualised, represented, and mobilised as cultural heritage.

Consistent with WP4's commitment to a flexible and transdisciplinary framework, the workshop encouraged participants to interrogate disciplinary assumptions,

including about what counts as evidence, how culinary knowledge should be documented, whether recipes should be treated primarily as texts, practices, data, performances, or heritage objects, and how authority is assigned to written, oral, embodied, institutional, or community-based forms of knowledge. In doing so, the workshop made these assumptions explicit and used them as the basis for developing new methodological approaches to the study of recipes as dynamic cultural artefacts.

The workshop consisted of eight thematically sequenced sessions:

1. Ingredients
2. Cooking
3. Preserving
4. Serving
5. Power and Politics
6. Identity and Heritage
7. The Digital Turn
8. Authorship and Aesthetics

Moving from material substrates to embodied practice, from textual, transcribed, and oral transmissions to the digital turn, and from collective tradition to individual creativity, the program itself functioned as a methodological argument.

Figure 3: Anthropologist Ariana Gunderson (Indiana University Bloomington) presents on recipe developers. October 2025. Pollenzo.

The diversity of approaches represented at the workshop also underscored the need for a more systematic framework for recipe studies. While recipes are widely recognised as important sources for understanding food cultures, they are often analysed through disciplinary lenses that privilege different forms of evidence, scales of analysis, and recipe definitions. This diversity is intellectually productive, but it can also make comparison, collaboration, and digital integration difficult. The workshop therefore sought to avoid imposing a single methodology and instead identify a shared conceptual vocabulary capable of supporting interdisciplinary dialogue and the development of WP5's digital and pedagogical outputs.

WP5 operates on the premise that recipes are not only prescriptive culinary texts, but historically layered cultural artefacts shaped by movements of people, ingredients, technologies, and ideas. In alignment with the objectives of WP5, the workshop sought to articulate and refine a methodological framework structured around three interconnected concepts: **mobility, agency, and interdisciplinarity**.

Mobility was explored through ingredient substitution, migration, translation, trade networks, and digital circulation. Ingredient lists emerged as cultural narratives whose absences and substitutions index ecological conditions, social hierarchies, language, literacy, and transnational exchanges.

Agency was examined through questions of authorship, personalisation, marginalia, gendered labour, and political authority. Recipes were shown to operate simultaneously as descriptive records and prescriptive claims, thereby articulating not only what was cooked, but what ought to be cooked.

Interdisciplinarity was treated as necessity and principle. Contributions integrated manuscript philology, digital humanities, oral history, sensory design research, heritage studies, and more. The workshop also highlighted tensions between language and materiality: recipes often rely on textual fidelity, yet food as a material object resists stability, depending on tacit knowledge and embodied practice.

2.1 Purpose

The purpose of the workshop was to address the need for a **systematic methodology for working with recipes** within food studies and cultural heritage research.

Although recipes are frequently used as sources of data, evidence, and interpretation, they are often approached differently across disciplines, with historians, anthropologists, folklorists, literary scholars, digital humanists, and heritage practitioners assigning different meanings to the recipe as text, practice, object, performance, or dataset. The workshop therefore sought to bring these perspectives

into conversation and to develop a **shared methodological orientation** capable of supporting collaboration across WP5.

A central purpose of the workshop was therefore to consolidate a shared analytical vocabulary across disciplines and to align conceptual reflection with the practical requirements of digital implementation. This meant asking how categories developed through historical, anthropological, literary, folkloric, sensory, and heritage-based approaches to recipes could be translated into terms useful for dataset construction, visualisation design, teaching materials, and the edited volume.

Through this structure, the workshop established a framework capable of guiding subsequent WP5 activities, particularly the development of the recipe dataset and visualisation prototype under T5.2. It also created a common intellectual foundation for the edited volume, which will extend the workshop's methodological reflections into a broader scholarly contribution to recipe studies.

2.2 Problem-based framework

The framework for the workshop was designed around a methodological problem: recipes are widely used across food studies and cultural heritage research, but they are not always studied through a shared set of questions, concepts, or procedures.

Depending on the discipline, a recipe may be treated as a historical document, a literary form, a set of instructions, an archive of tacit knowledge, an object of memory, a performance, a data point, or a unit for digital visualisation. Each of these approaches is valuable, but each also carries different assumptions about what counts as evidence, what should be preserved, and how culinary knowledge should be interpreted.

For WP5, the challenge was to gather examples of recipe research and then create a setting in which these different approaches could be compared, questioned, and brought into a more systematic methodological conversation.

This challenge also connected directly to the critical framework developed in D4.1, which frames culinary heritage as dynamic, embodied, relational, and difficult to reduce to fixed documentation or static outputs. For WP5, this meant that recipes had to be approached not only as sources to be analysed, but also as cultural artefacts whose collection, selection, storage, translation, and visualisation involve **interpretive choices**. Moving recipes from academic analysis into an edited volume, teaching materials, and a digital platform therefore requires explicit decisions about such choices.

A central premise of the workshop was that existing approaches to recipes in food studies, the humanities, and the social sciences often rely on **unspoken methodological assumptions**. Recipes can be used as sources of historical, cultural, or social evidence. Yet, they are rarely examined as **methodological objects** in their own right.

For example, in many humanities approaches, recipes are treated primarily as texts to be interpreted, contextualised, and compared. In social science and ethnographic approaches, they are often approached as evidence of practice, identity, memory, labour, or community belonging. In heritage studies, recipes may be framed as carriers of tradition, while in digital humanities they can become data points to be encoded, classified, visualised, and circulated.

These approaches are all productive within their fields. From a cross-disciplinary perspective, however, they generate unresolved questions:

What counts as evidence?

How can tacit or embodied knowledge be documented?

How should change and variation be represented?

How recipes can be translated into shared categories without reducing their cultural complexity?

The workshop was designed to make these assumptions explicit and ask how scholarly approaches to recipes can be developed into a systematic framework for WP5's edited volume, educational materials, dataset, and visualisation prototype.

More specifically, this process involved identifying specific conceptual tensions out of the lack of systematic methodological framework, in order to generate productive analytical categories. Tensions included relationships between:

- recipe vs. dish
- written text vs. embodied practice
- preservation vs. transformation
- individual authorship vs. collective transmission
- analogue sources vs. digital infrastructures

Making these tensions explicit created workshop conditions for a methodology that could remain both open to disciplinary difference and facilitating shared terms for comparison and collaboration.

Figure 4: WP5 Lead and historian Simone Cinotto (University of Gastronomic Sciences) addresses audience. October 2025. Pollenzo.

2.3 Scholarly and pragmatic needs

The workshop framework was designed to connect scholarly analysis with the practical requirements of later WP5 outputs. T5.2 depends on developing a recipe dataset and visualisation prototype. First, the workshop had to consider how concepts such as mobility, agency, and interdisciplinarity could become usable analytical categories. The framework would then link to reflection regarding data structure, metadata, source selection, and visualisation.

First, we asked: What information needs to be captured in order to represent the movement of recipes, ingredients, people, techniques, and meanings across time and space? How does one account for forms of knowledge that are tacit, oral, embodied, or incomplete? How does one avoid reducing culinary heritage to static or purely textual representations?

To translate these questions into the workshop format, we decided to bring together two complementary forms of expertise: 1) Invited methodological interventions were included to address broader conceptual and disciplinary questions, such as the ontology of recipes, the role of sensory and embodied knowledge, the politics of culinary heritage, and the implications of digital preservation. 2) Accepted case study

papers were selected to test these questions against specific historical, geographical, and media contexts. The combination of these formats allowed the workshop to move between general methodological reflection and concrete examples of how recipes operate in practice.

2.4 Interdisciplinarity and interconnections

Selecting papers needed to fill a broad range of research areas relevant to WP5. The final program included expertise in food history, anthropology, folklore, literary studies, manuscript studies, digital humanities, sensory studies, heritage studies, and design research. It also included work on manuscript, printed, oral, and digital recipe cultures; on European, diasporic, and comparative non-European contexts; and on themes such as migration, substitution, authorship, gender, political authority, identity, aesthetics, and digital archiving.

This range was essential because the methodological framework would lack adaptability if generated from a single discipline or source type. Multiple fields and subject areas would allow us to test a systematic methodology against diverse forms of evidence and different ways of defining a recipe.

The resulting framework centres on three interconnected concepts: **mobility, agency, and interdisciplinarity**. Mobility provides a way to analyse how recipes, ingredients, techniques, and meanings travel across regions, communities, languages, and media. Agency allows the framework to account for the people and institutions that create, adapt, authorise, transmit, preserve, or contest recipes, including cooks, compilers, publishers, states, families, communities, and digital platforms. Interdisciplinarity functions as both principle and a method, ensuring that recipes encourage multiple forms of evidence and are not reduced to one disciplinary definition.

2.5 Summary of design

The MFW was both conceptual and operational. Conceptually, it clarified why recipes should be understood as dynamic cultural artefacts rather than fixed culinary instructions. Operationally, it identified the kinds of questions, categories, and source relationships that will guide dataset construction, visualisation design, pedagogical outputs, and the edited volume.

This shift from academic discussion to methodological guidance is central to WP5. The aim is to make recipe analysis usable across formats, including a scholarly volume, teaching materials, and a public-facing digital platform. The framework therefore bridges the workshop itself with the broader trajectory of WP5, ensuring

that the methodological insights generated in Pollenzo inform the next stages of RELISH research, digital development, and dissemination.

To make this framework operational for subsequent WP5 activities, the workshop discussions can be summarised through the following interconnected dimensions (see **Table 1**). Please note that these dimensions should function as a flexible taxonomy linking methodological reflection, case study evidence, and future digital, pedagogical, and dissemination outputs.

Table 1: The Methodological Framework Workshop (MFW) at-a-glance.

FRAMEWORK DIMENSION	KEY METHODOLOGICAL QUESTION	ILLUSTRATIVE WORKSHOP CONTRIBUTIONS	WP5 RELEVANCE
Recipe, dish, cookbook, practice	What exactly is the object of analysis: the recipe, the dish, the cookbook, the ingredient, the cooking practice, or the heritage object?	Daniel Bender, Michelle King, L. Sasha Gora, Ariana Gunderson	Clarifies the unit of analysis for the edited volume, dataset construction, and visualisation design
Mobility and transformation	How do recipes, ingredients, techniques, and meanings move across regions, communities, languages, and media?	Yanet Acosta, Lucy Long, Barbara Denicolò, Simone Cinotto, Gabriele Proglio	Supports analysis of circulation, migration, substitution, adaptation, and identity formation
Agency and authority	Who creates, adapts, authorises, preserves, contests, or transmits recipes?	Danielle Callegari, Diana Mincyte, Claudia Sbuttoni, Lucy Long	Connects recipes to questions of power, authorship, legitimacy, heritage formation, and cultural authority
Embodiment and tacit knowledge	What forms of knowledge are left outside the written recipe but remain essential to cooking and transmission?	Amy Bentley, Fabio Parasecoli, Zihan Guo, Regina Sexton, Gabriele Proglio	Accounts for sensory practice, gesture, material environments, tools, and embodied expertise
Interdisciplinarity and method	How can different disciplinary approaches to recipes be brought into dialogue without reducing recipes to a single definition?	Contributions across food history, anthropology, folklore, literary studies, digital humanities, sensory studies, and heritage studies	Establishes a shared analytical vocabulary across disciplines and supports WP5 collaboration

FRAMEWORK DIMENSION	KEY METHODOLOGICAL QUESTION	ILLUSTRATIVE WORKSHOP CONTRIBUTIONS	WP5 RELEVANCE
Digital mediation and visualisation	What happens when recipes are transcribed, encoded, classified, visualised, and made accessible through digital platforms?	Helmut Klug, Daniel Newman, James Malin, Yanet Acosta, Lisa Smith	Links the MFW to T5.2, including dataset development, metadata design, visualisation requirements, and collaboration with RELISH technical partners
Pedagogy and public engagement	How can recipes be used not only as research sources, but also as accessible tools for teaching, storytelling, and public engagement?	Workshop discussions and forthcoming “Teaching with Recipes” materials	Connects the workshop framework to RELISH’s broader innovation: using recipes as cultural, educational, and digital tools

3 Activities

The preparation for the workshop began with a collective reflection within WP5 on the methodological gap that the event was intended to address:

Context: Recipes are widely used in food studies, food history, anthropology, folklore, literary studies, digital humanities, and heritage research, but they are often treated differently from one discipline to another. In some contexts, recipes are read as texts; in others, as evidence of practice, memory, identity, labour, taste, mobility, or social belonging.

Gap: Recipe methods and advances are siloed and constrained, thus warranting systematic methodological discussion.

From this gap, WP5 designed the workshop to move from theoretical and scholarly engagement with recipes toward a more explicit methodological and digital framework capable of supporting dataset construction, data visualisation, teaching, scholarly publication, and dissemination.

Before drafting the Call for Papers (CfP), the WP5 team identified a set of areas where existing discussions around recipes, mobility, interdisciplinarity, and cultural heritage required further development. In particular, the team sought to address:

- Tendencies to invoke mobility without always specifying how movement can be traced methodologically
- References to interdisciplinarity without always defining how different forms of evidence can be brought into relation
- Uses of recipes as sources that lack clarity regarding whether the object of analysis is the recipe, the dish, the cookbook, the ingredient, the practice, or the community of transmission

The workshop was therefore designed to make these distinctions explicit and to ask how they could be translated into analytical categories useful for WP5.

3.1 Proposal selection

WP5 developed the CfP around this rationale and disseminated it through broader food studies listservs, professional channels, and RELISH networks. Rather than seeking papers on recipes in a topical sense, WP5 aimed to attract contributions that would help build a methodological framework for understanding recipes as dynamic cultural artefacts. In particular, WP5 looked for paper proposals that spoke to different source types, including manuscript, printed, oral, and digital recipes; different disciplinary traditions, including history, anthropology, folklore, literary studies, digital humanities, sensory studies, and heritage studies; and different thematic concerns, including mobility, substitution, authorship, embodiment, identity, power, gender, sustainability, and digital preservation.

The resulting program would be one that featured selected participants who would introduce broad methodological reflection and those would present concrete case studies capable of testing and refining the framework.

Over 60 proposals were received from scholars around the world and from a range of disciplinary backgrounds. Given the scope and format of the event, WP5 undertook a selective evaluation process, resulting in the acceptance of 21 presenters.

Paper proposals were evaluated according to:

- Their **relevance** to WP5's core concepts of mobility, agency, and interdisciplinarity
- The **clarity** of their methodological contribution
- The **originality** of their source or case study

- Demonstrated interest in approaching **recipes as cultural heritage** rather than only as culinary instructions
- Their **potential to contribute** to later WP5 outputs, including the dataset, visualisation prototype, teaching materials, and edited volume

Particular attention was given to proposals that moved beyond descriptive accounts of recipes and engage with methodological opportunities and constraints in how recipes can be analysed, compared, preserved, or translated into digital and pedagogical formats.

As a result, the selected contributions brought new archives, source types, disciplinary perspectives, and analytical questions into dialogue, helping WP5 examine recipes as evidence of mobility, embodied knowledge, authorship, identity, power, sustainability, and cultural transmission across diverse historical, geographical, and media contexts.

3.2 Logistics and promotion

The workshop took place at UNISG from 22–25 October 2025 and brought together the selected presenters, consortium members, and a wider audience that ranged between 50–100 audience participants, depending on the session.

UNISG coordinated the logistical and organisational aspects of the event, including: Communication with participants; Scheduling, flight arrangements, hotel bookings, local transportation, dinners, and hospitality services; Reimbursements and financial administration; Institutional visibility activities; Arranging photography and video services to document the workshop and support its dissemination; Producing promotional and practical materials (e.g., workshop brochure, posters, name tags).

Logistical and communication work supported other attending RELISH partners' clarity among on analytical and methodological approaches,¹ external engagement, and feedback. Promotion also sought to enhance impact and dissemination via:

- High visibility through cross-promotion between UNISG and RELISH communication channels (particularly Instagram)²

¹ Non-WP5 RELISH members from UDUR, BSC, and UMIL also attended.

² **Instagram cross-posting** (@relish_he & @unisg_official):

- CfP promotion (6 October 2025): [\[LINK\]](#)

- RELISH Instagram Internal Recap (29 October 2025): [\[LINK\]](#)

- Beneficiary Recap (21 November 2025): [\[LINK\]](#)

- Endorsement by a visible public figure, the late Carlo Petrini (former President and Founder of Slow Food and UNISG)
- Presence of non-panelist attendees, particularly one of RELISH’s target audiences (emerging adults)
- Building a stakeholder network and amplifying participant projects and expertise on RELISH communication channels

Figure 5: Workshop program. October 2025. Pollenzo.

3.3 Workshop format

The program was structured around a series of key methodological questions:

- What is a recipe, and how does it differ from a dish, a cookbook, an ingredient list, or a culinary practice?
- What kinds of evidence do recipes provide, and what forms of knowledge do they leave implicit?
- How can researchers trace mobility, authorship, power, identity, taste, labour, and transmission through recipes without reducing them to static textual objects?
- How can recipes be studied across manuscript, printed, oral, and digital forms?
- And how can these questions be translated into categories useful for dataset construction, visualisation, teaching, and public engagement?

To address these questions, the workshop used several complementary formats.

First, the program opened with a **roundtable** featuring four scholars from the UNISG History group (Simone Cinotto, Claudia Sbuttoni, Gabriele Proglia, Elisa Pastorelli), which situated the workshop within the beneficiary institution's broader intellectual environment, and introduced historical and methodological problems that would recur throughout the event.

Second, **invited methodological interventions** were scheduled to address broader conceptual questions central to WP5, including the ontology of recipes, the relationship between recipes and cookbooks, tacit and embodied knowledge, sensory practice, digital preservation, and the politics of culinary heritage.

Third, **accepted case study papers** then tested methodological interventions against specific historical, geographical, and media contexts.

Finally, dedicated **discussion sessions** translated the conceptual debates into operational categories for WP5, particularly for dataset development and the recipe visualisation prototype (T5.2).

Within sessions, participants examined recipes through ingredient semantics and substitution; embodiment and the limits of instruction; digital philology and preservation ethics; oral transmission and vernacular traditions; culinary governance and ideology; diasporic identity; early web food cultures; and authorship and aesthetic recombination.

3.4 Participants

The full list of invited and accepted participants, their affiliations, and presentations is provided below.

Table 2: MFW participants for October 2025 event, in order of presentation.

NAME	AFFILIATION	PRESENTATION TITLE
Simone Cinotto, Elisa Pastorelli, Gabriele Progllo, Claudia Sbuttoni	University of Gastronomic Sciences	“UNISG History Roundtable: Recipes and Cultural Heritage at UNISG”
Daniel E. Bender and Jeffrey Newman	University of Toronto	“Recipes, Substitution, and the Age of Mechanical Reproduction”
L. Sasha Gora	Universität Augsburg	“Tongues and Their Mothers, Ingredients and Their Understudies”
Amy Bentley	New York University	“Recipes and Methodologies: Decoding the Paratext”
Michelle King	University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	“Recipes and Culinary Relationships in Historical Context: A Chinese Counterpoint to Possible European Patterns”
Fabio Parasecoli	New York University	“Bringing Dishes into Reality: The Design and Sensory Aspects of Recipes”
Daniel Newman	Durham University	“A Balanced Temperament: Using Advanced Natural Language Processing Methods in the Analysis of Medieval Arabic Recipes”
Helmut W. Klug	Universität Graz	“Researching Medieval Culinary Recipes with Digital Humanities Methods: The Cooking Recipes of the Middle Ages Project”
Regina Sexton	University College Cork	“Bridging Oral and Textual Narratives: Methodological Approaches to Conceptualizing the Recipe in Irish Folk Tradition”
Lisa W. Smith	University of Essex	“3000 Dishes on an Excel Table, or Approaches to Organizing Information in Recipes”
Danielle Callegari	Dartmouth College	“The Liber de coquina of Federico II”
Diana Mincyte	City University of New York City Tech	“Cocktails from Above: Drink Recipes and the Making of Socialist Heritage”
Barbara Denicolò	Universität Salzburg	“Pre-modern Worlds in a Recipe; Or What Do I Have to Know about Cooking ‘Good’ Food?”

Lucy Long	The Center for Food and Culture	“Irish Soda Bread Recipes in US as Documents of Ethnicity”
María Yanet Acosta Meneses	Universidad Rey Juan Carlos	“English Influence Through Recipes: The Case of Handwritten Recipe Booknotes from the Canary Islands”
James E. Malin	Cooper Union	“Stale Breadcrumbs: Digital Food Historiography of Web 1.0”
Zihan Guo	Princeton University	“‘Make It Pleasant’: Aesthetic Expressions in Household Recipes in Eighteenth-Century England”
Ariana Gunderson	Indiana University Bloomington	“Whose Recipe Is This? Authorship and Originality in the German Recipe Industry”
<p>Non-presenting participants:</p> <p>Matthieu Belledent (Technological University Dublin); Andrea Borghini (Università degli Studi di Milano); Kathleen Burke (National University of Singapore); Federica Fortugno (UNISG); Roger Gonzalez March (Barcelona Supercomputing Center); Sara Madera Gomez (Università degli Studi di Milano); Ilaria Ravazzolo (University of Warwick); Norman Rusin (Salve Regina University); Rosi Song (Durham University); sahar tavakoli (Università degli Studi di Milano); Gary Thompson (Technological University Dublin); Janita Van Dyk (Durham University); Heather Yeatman (Boston University).</p>		

3.5 Identifying specific problem areas

During sessions, WP5 team members and RELISH participants took note of specific challenges and problem areas frequently arose.

Throughout, the political and cultural dimensions of collecting, storing, interpreting, and using **recipes as cultural artefacts** became a recurring concern. This discussion directly connects to WP4’s D4.1, “Critical Framework for RELISH,”³ which frames culinary Intangible Cultural Heritage (cICH) dynamic and relational qualities difficult to reduce to fixed documentation. D4.1 identifies documentation, representation, and safeguarding as central challenges for RELISH: How can culinary knowledge be recorded without detaching it from practice, community, memory, and change?

The workshop extended this concern to recipes specifically by asking how transcription, selection, classification, metadata design, and visualisation participate in shaping culinary heritage rather than simply preserving it. In this sense,

³ D4.1 can be found on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/19922981>

participants underscored the need for approaching recipes as methodological tools that can illuminate how **documentary practices** involve cultural and political choices.

For this reason, digital preservation and visualisation were addressed explicitly as non-neutral methodological and curatorial practices. Discussions emphasised that transcription, encoding, metadata design, and algorithmic classification shape which culinary pasts become visible, which forms of knowledge remain legible, and which relationships among recipes, ingredients, people, places, and practices can be represented.

Dedicated sessions therefore translated conceptual discussions into operational categories for dataset development under T5.2, ensuring that later work on the visualisation prototype would remain connected to the cultural, political, and methodological concerns raised by the workshop.

Figure 6: Historian Zihan Guo (Princeton University) presents on 18th-century recipe aesthetics with handwriting samples. October 2025. Pollenzo.

4 Results

The MFW resulted in the consolidation of a **shared analytical orientation** for WP5. In dialogue with the critical framework developed in D4.1, the workshop advanced a flexible methodology. This approach is consistent with the broader RELISH emphasis on culinary heritage as dynamic, embodied, relational, and limited when reduced to fixed documentation or static categories.

The workshop further refined WP4's wider cICH framework through the specific recipe cases that provide illustrative examples of how recipes can be analysed, compared, preserved, taught, and translated into digital forms without losing their historical, material, sensory, and cultural complexity.

4.1 Shared vocabulary

One of the main results of the workshop was consolidating a shared analytical vocabulary across disciplines and aligning conceptual reflection with digital implementation requirements.

Primarily, this vocabular stemmed from clarifying a fundamental analytical distinction within recipe studies—between *dish* and *recipe*.

Participants emphasised that recipes cannot be treated as transparent records of culinary practice, but must be understood in relation to broader textual, material, cultural, and social contexts. One of these key socio-material and embodied dynamics is between recipes and dishes. However, as framed by WP5 member, Daniel Bender, the “dish” and the “recipe” are not synonymous terms (see also Borghini 2015).

Recipes and dishes are often treated interchangeably in both public discourse and scholarly discussion. The workshop showed that separating them opens important theoretical and methodological possibilities. A recipe may prescribe, remember, authorise, standardise, adapt, or imagine a dish. However, it cannot reproduce the act of cooking or eating.

The distinction helped frame recipes as **mediating devices** rather than direct representations of historical consumption. More broadly, the workshop established that recipes operate between language and materiality, and that their meaning emerges through the interaction of text, embodied practice, sensory knowledge, and cultural context.

Figure 7: WP5 member, historian, and food writer Regina Sexton (University College Cork) presents research. October 2025. Pollenzo.

4.2 Methodological themes

Across the papers, a set of interlocking methodological themes emerged that collectively shaped the framework for WP5.

A first key insight concerned the **unstable form of the recipe**, particularly the relationship between textuality, orality, embodiment, and practice:

Regina Sexton’s work (University College Cork) on Irish vernacular food tradition showed that recipes do not always appear in normative written form, and emphasised frictions between “original,” “authored” archetypes and those embedded in oral narratives, transcribed accounts, and vernacular systems of knowledge.

Contributions by Amy Bentley (New York University) and Fabio Parasecoli (New York University) further demonstrated that recipes must be read through their paratextual traces, sensory dimensions, and performative enactment.

Methodological approaches to recipes that only engage them as explicit written instructions (and which is heavily represented in currently humanities literature) inadvertently omit crucial forms of tacit knowledge, including how a texture should feel, how heat should be judged, how much variation is acceptable, what tools or ingredients are assumed, and what forms of practical experience the reader is expected to bring. A recipe's textual incompleteness can therefore reframe what is commonly considered a problem or gap in data as a methodological insight and analytical opportunity that directs attention to manifold phenomena: gesture, memory, habit, material environment, oral transmission, and embodied expertise.

Textual-non-textual intersections provoke questions regarding whether all recipe-like materials fit neatly within a single methodological model, or whether the framework must remain flexible enough to accommodate instructions, notes, oral traditions, ingredient lists, cookbooks, marginalia, transcriptions, and digital records.

A second major theme concerned **mobility, exchange, and transformation**:

Papers by Yanet Acosta (Universidad Rey Juan Carlos), Lucy Long (The Center for Food and Culture), and Barbara Denicolò (Universität Salzburg) showed how recipes move across regions, media, and communities, registering histories of migration, trade, translation, and cultural adaptation.

Recipes dynamism can paradoxically preserve *and* transform identity, functioning as sites where continuity and change coexist. These contributions gave concrete substance to the “mobility” dimension of the framework by showing that movement can be traced through specific methodological indicators: ingredients, substitutions, language, manuscript circulation, publication history, oral transmission, domestic practice, and digital redistribution. Mobility was therefore understood as a set of historical and cultural processes that can be investigated through recipes.

A third theme addressed **power, politics, and the processes of heritage formation**:

Danielle Callegari's work (Dartmouth College) on the *Liber de coquina*, Diana Mincyte's analysis (City University of New York City Tech) of socialist-era cocktail recipes, and Claudia Sbuttoni's research (University of Gastronomic Sciences) on the invention of culinary heritage in Trieste each illustrated how recipes can function as instruments of authority, ideological expression, or contested cultural production.

Lucy Long's work highlighted how recipes operate as sites of negotiation over identity and authenticity.

Figure 8: WP5 members Daniel Bender (University of Toronto) and Jeffrey Newman (University of Toronto) present research combining culinary historical methods with library and information sciences. October 2025. Pollenzo.

Recipes as techniques of authority and power connected directly to D4.1's concern with the cultural and political dimensions of documenting, representing, and safeguarding cICH. The workshop extended this concern to recipes by showing that decisions about what to collect, classify, preserve, publish, or visualise are never neutral. Recipes are implicated in questions of legitimacy, inclusion/exclusion, ownership, community recognition, and cultural authority.

Questions of **authorship, classification, and conceptual precision** constituted a fourth theme.

Contributions by L. Sasha Gora (Universität Augsburg) and Ariana Gunderson (Indiana University Bloomington) explored the elasticity of recipes, the politics of substitution and naming, and the iterative nature of authorship.

Michelle King (University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill) further challenged participants to reflect on the appropriate unit of analysis; whether ingredient, dish, recipe, cookbook, commensal group, or culinary practice.

Taken together with Regina Sexton’s discussion of recipes in oral and transcribed traditions and Lisa Wynne Smith’s analysis of recipe categorisation in digital datasets, these discussions reinforced the need for greater conceptual clarity and methodological reflexivity. They also substantiated ontological questions raised by WP4 in asking what exactly counts as a recipe for the purposes of historical analysis, cultural heritage work, dataset construction, and digital visualisation.

A further fifth contribution came from papers addressing **digital mediation, categorisation, and preservation.**

Lisa Wynne Smith’s work (University of Essex) on the challenges of categorising recipe data showed that recipes can at first appear deceptively easy to describe in databases. They become far more difficult to classify once researchers account for their density, flexibility, marginalia, ingredients, authorship, public uses, and future interoperability. Her comparison of digital recipe projects, particularly the Early Modern Recipe Online Collective (EMROC)⁴ demonstrated that datasets are shaped as much by cultural heritage goals and public engagement needs as they are by individual or institutional research priorities.

Helmut Klug’s presentation (Universität Graz) of the CoReMA project,⁵ alongside reflections by Daniel Newman (Durham University) and James Malin (Cooper Union), further demonstrated how digital tools—such as semantic annotation, data modelling, and visualisation—can provide new opportunities for analysing culinary texts, yet require parsing the politics and archival responsibilities regarding how to standardise data and make it interoperable. Yanet Acosta’s digital repository of handwritten recipe notebooks⁶ provided one model for this via Open Access dissemination.

Collectively, these contributions showed concretely why digital work is its own and increasingly significant methodological domain. Transcription decides what is included or excluded from the record; encoding turns interpretive judgments into structured categories; metadata design determines which relationships can be searched, compared, or visualised; and attending visualisations shape how users perceive movement, influence, continuity, and change. These presentations

⁴ EMROC project site: <https://emroc.hypotheses.org/>

⁵ CoReMa project site: <https://gams.uni-graz.at/context:corema>

CoReMa’s datasets comprise a significant component for WP3’s historical recipe visualisation tool. See D3.3, “RELISH Dataset from Digitised EU Recipe Collections and IP Issues,” available on Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/records/19374402>

⁶ *Recetas Canarias* project site: <https://recetascanarias.org/>

demonstrated that digital work, often glossed as dissemination activities, actively structures how recipe knowledge becomes legible, comparable, and usable. This point is valuable for RELISH’s own data and platform development.

Finally, several papers highlighted **identity, aesthetics, and reflexivity** as key methodological concerns.

Lucy Long’s work on soda bread as a marker of ethnicity, Zihan Guo’s (Princeton University) focus on taste and visuality in early modern recipes, and Barbara Denicolò’s reflections on historical continuity all demonstrated that recipes encode values, aspirations, and forms of cultural belonging.

These contributions reinforced the “agency” dimension of the framework, showing that recipes are sites where meanings are negotiated rather than simply transmitted and accepted. Presenters also emphasised that researchers should reflect on their own categories of analysis, especially when moving between disciplines and media formats.

Figure 9: L. Sasha Gora (Universität Augsburg) presents on the elasticity of recipes and ingredients. October 2025. Pollenzo.

4.3 RELISH dataset and prototype applications

Conceptually, mobility, agency, and interdisciplinarity were thus established as interdependent analytical dimensions. *Practically*, the workshop helped define the kinds of variables, relationships, and interpretive questions that will guide dataset construction under T5.2.

We have gathered these dimensions to include:

- The nature of the recipe as text and practice
- Recipes' embodied and performative qualities
- Ingredient trajectories
- Modes of transmission
- Cultural and social contexts
- Authorship and authority
- Heritage claims
- Technological mediation
- Degrees of uncertainty or incompleteness attached to a source

The workshop contributes to the epistemological foundation of the forthcoming recipe visualisation prototype by clarifying what counts as a unit of analysis, what relationships should be modelled, what forms of knowledge risk being lost in digitisation, and how the platform can represent recipes as dynamic cultural artefacts.

4.4 Absences and gaps

The workshop also surfaced productive gaps that will inform the forthcoming edited volume and future WP5 outputs:

- The need for deeper gender analysis in recipe transmission
- Clearer conceptual boundaries around heritage, authenticity, and community recognition
- Greater attention to television, social media, and other mass media in recipe circulation
- More explicit treatment of labour, domestic work, and embodied expertise

4.5 Additional and potential outcomes

The outcomes of the workshop also point to several areas of application beyond the academic volume. **Academically**, the workshop supported the consolidation of recipe studies as a field with recipes as sources *and* as methodological objects that raise ontological, epistemological, and interpretive questions. **Pedagogically**, the MFW reinforced one of RELISH's central innovations: the use of recipes as accessible and adaptable tools for teaching and student-centred learning across educational contexts. From the perspective of **public engagement**, the workshop also showed how recipes can be used to construct, communicate, and diversify understandings of food heritage, identity, and cultural values. These applications confirm that the framework developed through T5.1 is relevant not only for teaching, digital storytelling, community engagement, and future-facing heritage work.

Overall, the workshop therefore ensured continuity between methodological development, pedagogical innovation, and scientific dissemination by converting collective discussion into concrete outputs.

The analytical vocabulary and methodological questions developed during the event will guide the edited volume, provide case material and conceptual structure for the "Teaching with Recipes" educational materials, and inform the dataset and visualisation prototype under T5.2. In this way, the workshop fulfilled the objectives of T5.1 by establishing a methodological framework that supports WP5's subsequent research, digital development, teaching, and dissemination activities.

5 Dissemination

The workshop demonstrated strong scholarly interest in developing systematic approaches to recipes as methodological, pedagogical, and digital tools within food studies and cultural heritage research. The level of interest and engagement demonstrated stakeholders are keen to address issues of under-theorisation of and applications with recipes. These new alignments will help bolster project goals reconsidering the concrete roles recipes could play as methodological and connective tools for both established scholars and new publics and users.

Audience participation, ranging from fifty to one hundred attendees across sessions, further reinforced the relevance of the topic beyond the consortium and confirmed the value of RELISH's effort to position recipes as tools for teaching, public engagement, and digital storytelling.

Figure 10: The late Arab food scholar and translator Daniel Newman (WP5 member, Durham University) presents research. October 2025. Pollenzo.

The workshop also demonstrated the methodological richness of the field by bringing together diverse disciplinary perspectives and analytical approaches. In this respect,

“The workshop was successful in elucidating the existence of the recipe in a plurality of forms.” (Regina Sexton, WP5)

This plurality reinforces the need for flexible, interdisciplinary methodologies capable of accommodating the varied ways in which recipes contribute to forms of cultural heritage. Recipes derive their cultural significance not from completeness or standardisation, but from their interpretive openness; indeed,

“Recipes are necessarily incomplete, and their incompleteness is what makes them culturally powerful.” (Daniel Newman, WP5)

Institutional communication activities amplified the visibility of the event. UNISG prepared and circulated a press release and supported the dissemination of the workshop through posts on Instagram, Facebook, and LinkedIn. These

communications were further reposted and amplified by participants and by RELISH, extending the event's reach beyond those physically present and reinforcing its role within the project's wider public and academic visibility strategy.

The MFW's outcomes are being further extended through the preparation of an **edited volume** and integration into teaching and public engagement initiatives.

Furthermore, the workshop made visible RELISH as a new voice in debates on recipes, cultural heritage, and digital humanities.

More broadly, the methodological framework developed during the workshop contributes to RELISH's overarching objective of reframing European gastronomic heritage as dynamic, hybrid, relational, and shaped by exchange. Through MFW and ongoing outputs, WP5 advances a conception of European identity that centres interaction and cultural mobility.

6 Conclusion

The **Methodological Framework Workshop (MFW)** held at UNISG from 22–25 October 2025 established a methodological framework for recipe analysis and substantiated with external and internal partners the significance of identifying methods and frameworks research and digital applications with recipes. Likewise, the MFW validated within the academy as an object of historical, cultural, digital, and pedagogical inquiry.

D5.1 resulted in a coherent, adaptable, and critically examined framework for analysing recipes as mobile, agentic, embodied, and interdisciplinary cultural artefacts. In doing so, it articulated a historically grounded and methodologically plural vision for recipe studies and culinary heritage research.

Across its thematic progression, the workshop demonstrated that recipes mediate matter and meaning, memory and power, sensory practice and textual representation. They are neither marginal nor purely functional sources, and instead are privileged instruments for understanding how culinary knowledge is produced, circulated, contested, embodied, remembered, and even abandoned and forgotten.

The workshop also strengthened the connection between scholarly inquiry and the practical needs of WP5. The MFW's discussions provided a shared analytical vocabulary that can support the edited volume, the "Teaching with Recipes" educational materials, and the recipe dataset and visualisation prototype under T5.2. In particular, the framework helps define which aspects of recipes need to be made

visible in future WP5 outputs, including ingredients, substitutions, modes of transmission, authorship, cultural context, embodied knowledge, uncertainty, and digital mediation. These categories provide a basis for dialogue with RELISH technical partners, including work being developed with BSC and IST around data structures, platform requirements, and visualisation possibilities.

As such, the Methodological Framework Workshop fulfils both the intellectual and practical commitments of T5.1, consolidating the methodological orientation of WP5 and advancing RELISH's broader ambition to reframe European gastronomic heritage as dynamic, relational, inclusive, and accessible across academic, pedagogical, and digital contexts.

Figure 11: Group photo of workshop in front of the main UNISG campus buildings. October 2025. Pollenzo.

Annex I: Edited Volume Materials

Edited volume proposal for *Recipes as Cultural Heritage: Meaning, Methodology, and Media*. Submitted to Routledge Press.

Full proposal:

Recipes as Cultural Heritage: Meaning, Methodology, and Media explores the histories, practices, and knowledge embedded in recipes, showing how they do far more than tell us what to cook. Recipes are cultural artifacts: they carry social meanings, shape identities, and reflect political, economic, and technological contexts. This volume brings together scholars from food studies, heritage studies, history, anthropology, and digital humanities to examine recipes as agents of cultural heritage, highlighting their role in transmitting knowledge, linking communities, and preserving cultural memory across time and space.

The book is organized around four interconnected questions: (1) how do recipes function as “sources” and objects of cultural heritage? (2) how do recipes participate in the construction and performance of personal, familial, and communal identities? (3) how do recipes illuminate questions of power and authority and intersect with social hierarchies and cultural politics? and (4) how do recipes circulate in a digital age and address the opportunities and challenges of preservation, categorization, and global exchange?

With case studies ranging across time and space, from early modern to contemporary European encounters, from handwritten manuscripts to globalized cookbooks, *Recipes as Cultural Heritage* combines historical analysis, archival research, ethnography, and advanced digital analysis. By situating recipes at the intersection of culture, media, and meaning, it offers an innovative framework for understanding culinary knowledge as a living form of heritage. *Recipes as Cultural Heritage* is intended to become the state-of-the-art work on its subject and be widely adopted in graduate and undergraduate courses in food studies, cultural heritage, history and related disciplines worldwide. Accessible, interdisciplinary, and empirically rich, the book speaks to scholars, students, and anyone interested in the histories, practices, and social significance of what we eat.

Keywords: Recipes; Cultural Heritage; Culinary Knowledge; Food History; Identity and Memory; Material Culture; Ethnography; Power and Politics of Food; Oral and Written Traditions; Digital Food Heritage; Global and Transnational Foodways; Methodologies in Food Studies; Archiving and Preservation; Digitization; Digital Humanities; Social Media.

Recipes as Cultural Heritage: Meaning, Methodology, and Media

Simone Cinotto and Claudia Sbuttoni, eds.

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- "Ontological Foundations for the Digital Archiving of Culinary Recipes" (Andrea Borghini)
- "Reading the Recipe: Paratexts and Marginalia" (Amy Bentley)
- "The Design and Sensory Aspects of Recipes as Cultural Heritage: The Practice of Embodied Epistemology" (Fabio Parasecoli)
- "Unveiling the Critical Nature of Cultural Heritage in Recipes" (Raúl Matta)

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- "Tongues and Their Mothers, Ingredients and Their Understudies" (L. Sasha Gora)
- "How the Sausage (Recipe) Gets Made: A Semiotic Theory of Recipes" (Ariana Gunderson)
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PART III - Recipes, Power, and Politics

- "Recipes and Culinary Relationships in Historical Context: A Chinese Counterpoint to Possible European Patterns" (Michelle T. King)
- "The Work of Culinary Art in the Age of Mechanical Reproduction" (Daniel E. Bender and Jeffrey Newman)
- "From Orality to Digitization: (Re)Translating the Language of Food in the Arbëreshë Community of Molise" (Elisa Pastorelli)
- "Le Teresiane: Inventing Culinary Heritage in Trieste" (Claudia Sbuttoni)
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- “The Cookies Are Crumbling: Recipes within the Incipient Infrastructures of Digital Food Historiography” (James Edward Malin)
- “Defining, Analyzing, and Understanding Late Medieval German Cooking Recipes in Their Cultural Context” (Helmut W. Klug)
- “Recipe Instagram: Identity, Influence, and Negotiation” (Emily J.H. Contois)
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Annex II: Workshop Programme

Full workshop programme is appended on the following pages.

Friday, October 24 (cont.)

3:45 pm - 4:00 pm - Coffee Break
Location: Tavole Accademiche (UNISG)

SESSION 7 - RECIPES AND THE DIGITAL TURN

4:15 pm - 5:45 pm, Aula Magna

María Yanet Acosta Meneses (Universidad Rey Juan Carlos), *English Influence Through Recipes: The Case of Handwritten Recipe Booknotes from the Canary Islands*

James Malin (Cooper Union), *Stale Breadcrumbs: Digital Food Historiography of Web 1.0*

Discussants: Daniel Newman (Durham University); Lisa Smith (University of Essex)

6:00 pm - 7:00 pm - Tour and wine tasting
Location: UNISG Banca del Vino

7:00 pm - 9:00 pm - Dinner
Location: Albergo dell'Agenzia

Saturday, October 25

SESSION 8 - AUTHORSHIP AND AESTHETICS

9:00 am - 10:30 am, Aula Magna

Zihan Guo (Princeton University), *"Make It Pleasant": Aesthetic Expressions in Household Recipes in Eighteenth-Century England*

Ariana Gunderson (Indiana University Bloomington), *Whose Recipe Is This? Authorship and Originality in the German Recipe Industry*

Discussants: Amy Bentley (New York University); L. Sasha Gora (Universität Augsburg)

This methodological workshop is organized within the framework of the EU-Horizon **RELISH** project (Reframing European Gastronomy Legacy through Innovation, Sustainability and Heritage, funded by the European Union – Project: 101177427 – RELISH– HORIZON – CL2–2024–HERITAGE–01) and aims to engage historians and other scholars across disciplines in discussions on the nature of recipes – how they are created, interpreted, shared, and transformed over time and across contexts.

Participants

Matthieu Belledent (Technological University Dublin); **Andrea Borghini** (Università degli Studi di Milano); **Anthony Buccini** (Independent Scholar); **Kathleen Burke** (National University of Singapore); **Michele Fontefrancesco** (Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore Milano); **Federica Fortugno** (UNISG); **Roger Gonzalez March** (Barcelona Supercomputing Center); **Sara Madera Gomez** (Università degli Studi di Milano); **Urszula Niewiadomska Flis** (Katolicki Uniwersytet Lubelski Jana Pawła II); **Ilaria Ravazzolo** (University of Warwick); **Norman Rusin** (Salve Regina University); **Rosi Song** (Durham University); **Sahar Tavakoli** (Università degli Studi di Milano); **Gary Thompson** (Technological University Dublin); **Janita Van Dyk** (Durham University); **Heather Yeatman** (Boston University); **Limor Yungman** (The Hebrew University of Jerusalem); **Xinwei Zhang** (University of Helsinki).

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Relish

**OCTOBER
22–25, 2025**

**Recipes and
Gastronomy as
Cultural Heritage**

**MEANING, METHODOLOGY,
AND MEDIA**

**The University of
Gastronomic Sciences**

Pollenzo, Italy

**Funded by
the European Union**

Wednesday, October 22

5:30 pm - Introduction of RELISH Network
Location: Casa B, Ristorante Battaglino (Bra)

Daniel E. Bender (University of Toronto)
Simone Cinotto (UNISG)
Daniel Newman (Durham University)
Claudia Sbuttoni (UNISG)
Regina Sexton (University College Cork)
Rosi Song (Durham University)

6:00 pm - UNISG History Team Roundtable

Recipes and Cultural Heritage at UNISG
with Simone Cinotto, Elisa Pastorelli,
Gabriele Proglgio, and Claudia Sbuttoni

7:30 pm - Dinner
Location: Ristorante Battaglino dal 1919 (Bra)

Thursday, October 23

Location: Aula Magna (UNISG)

9:30 am - Coffee and Registration

10:00 am - Opening Remarks from UNISG
Rector, Nicola Perullo

10:15 am - Opening Remarks from UNISG
President, Carlo Petrini

SESSION 1 - INGREDIENTS
10:45 am - 12:15 pm, Aula Magna

Daniel E. Bender (University of Toronto)
Jeff Newman (University of Toronto),
*Recipes, Substitution, and the Age of
Mechanical Reproduction*

L. Sasha Gora (Universität Augsburg),
*Tongues and Their Mothers, Ingredients and
Their Understudies*

Thursday, October 23 (cont.)

12:30 pm - 1:30 pm - Lunch
Location: Tavole Accademiche (UNISG)

SESSION 2 - COOKING
1:45 pm - 3:30 pm, Aula Magna

Amy Bentley (New York University), *Recipes
and Methodologies: Decoding the Paratext*

Michelle King (University of North Carolina
at Chapel Hill), *Recipes and Culinary
Relationships in Historical Context: A Chinese
Counterpoint to Possible European Patterns*

Fabio Parasecoli (New York University),
*Bringing Dishes into Reality: The Design and
Sensory Aspects of Recipes*

3:30 pm - 4:00 pm - Coffee Break
Location: Tavole Accademiche (UNISG)

SESSION 3 - PRESERVING
4:15 pm - 5:45 pm, Aula Magna

Daniel Newman (Durham University),
*A Balanced Temperament: Using Advanced
Natural Language Processing Methods in the
Analysis of Medieval Arabic Recipes*

Helmut W. Klug (Universität Graz),
*Researching Medieval Culinary Recipes with
Digital Humanities Methods: The Cooking
Recipes of the Middle Ages Project*

6:00 pm - Aperitivo and dinner
Location: Albergo Ristorante Real Castello di
Verduno

Friday, October 24

SESSION 4 - SERVING
9:30 am - 11:00 am, Aula Magna

Regina Sexton (University College Cork),
*Bridging Oral and Textual Narratives:
Methodological Approaches To Conceptualizing
the Recipe in Irish Folk Tradition*

Lisa W. Smith (University of Essex), *3000
Dishes on an Excel Table, or Approaches to
Organizing Information in Recipes*

11:00 am - 11:15 am - Coffee Break
Location: Aula Magna (UNISG)

SESSION 5 - POWER AND POLITICS
11:15 am - 12:45 pm, Aula Magna

Danielle Callegari (Dartmouth College), *The
Liber de coquina of Federico II*

Diana Mincyte (City University of New York
City Tech), *Cocktails from Above: Drink Recipes
and the Making of Socialist Heritage*

Discussants: Daniel Bender (University of
Toronto); Helmut W. Klug (Universität Graz)

1:00 pm - 2:00 pm - Lunch
Location: Tavole Accademiche (UNISG)

**SESSION 6 - RECIPES, IDENTITY,
HERITAGE**
2:15 pm - 3:45 pm, Aula Magna

Barbara Denicolò (Universität Salzburg), *Pre-
modern Worlds in a Recipe; Or What Do I Have
To Know about Cooking "Good" Food?*

Lucy Long (The Center for Food and Culture),
*Irish Soda Bread Recipes in US as Documents of
Ethnicity*

Discussants: Michelle King (University of
North Carolina at Chapel Hill); Regina Sexton
(University of College Cork)

Annex III: MFW Bibliography

MFW Bibliography (Selection)*

The following bibliography selection reflects the interdisciplinary scope of the workshop and provides a shared scholarly resource for future WP5 activities, including the edited volume, teaching materials, and further research on recipes as cultural heritage.

* A full organised bibliography will be released on the RELISH website in 2026 as a curated source for recipe research and culinary heritage.

Recipe definitions, methodology, and ontology

Foundational works on what recipes are, how they differ from dishes and cookbooks, and how they can be treated as methodological objects.

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